

April 2025

ALLEA STATEMENT ON CONTINUED ATTACKS ON ACADEMIC FREEDOM

In reaction to the most recent restrictions imposed by the U.S. Administration on the academic sector, the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, ALLEA, strongly re-affirms the importance of upholding the fundamental principles of academic freedom and institutional autonomy.

ALLEA remains deeply concerned by the continued censorship of research designs and publications in the U.S., the increasing marginalisation of scientifically relevant topics from public discourse, and the growing cuts to funding in different areas of research targeted at academic institutions. The new executive orders that freeze billions in federal research funding, including biomedical and environmental research, are likely to inflict severe harm on societies and peoples not only in the U.S., but globally. Recent political decisions risk undermining the invaluable role that science plays in creating benefits for society as a whole.

We feel encouraged by the overwhelming response to ALLEA's previous statement in February 2025 on [threats to academic freedom and international research collaboration in the United States](#), which reflects the unity shown by the more than 160 research institutions in Europe and beyond. This mobilisation reflects a shared understanding and commitment: defending academic freedom is an urgent and universal responsibility. We will continue to stand up against serious threats to the autonomy of science, which are incompatible with the principles of an open and democratic society.

This statement of ALLEA therefore calls upon all scientific institutions, political decision-makers, and the public to recognise and defend the essential role of independent science in the U.S. and worldwide, and to counteract a normalisation of these infringements on academic freedom. We express our strongest support and admiration for those academic institutions that stand up against political pressure and the recent governmental orders.¹

Clear regulatory frameworks are essential to shield academia from undue interference, guarantee rights for scholars and students, and maintain the autonomy of research. We therefore urge governments across the globe to refrain from coercive actions against academic institutions and instead call for a constructive dialogue that supports and protects the autonomy of research and higher education.

¹ See for example the [Open Letter](#) signed by more than 1900 members of the U.S. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, or the [Call for Constructive Engagement](#) initiated by the American Association of Colleges and Universities and the American Academy of Arts & Sciences.

About ALLEA

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing approximately 60 academies from 40 countries in Europe. Since its foundation in 1994, ALLEA speaks out on behalf of its members on the European and international stages, promotes science as a global public good, and facilitates scientific collaboration across borders and disciplines. Learn more here: <http://www.allea.org>.

Citation: For citation purposes, please use the following: ALLEA, ALLEA Statement on Continued Attacks on Academic Freedom (2025), ALLEA, DOI: [10.26356/ALLEA-STATEMENT-ACADEMIC-FREEDOM-ATTACKS](https://doi.org/10.26356/ALLEA-STATEMENT-ACADEMIC-FREEDOM-ATTACKS).

Licence: This work is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution licence, which permits unrestricted use, provided the original author and source are cited (CC BY 4.0). The detailed licence terms are available at <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>.